

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KATCHER-DUNNE****FIRST NAME: AMY****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: PERIOD 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied XUS UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author ~~X~~did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MSWord 2010 on Windows 10

ACA-401 COURSEPACK

1) INTRODUCTION

The ability to write a persuasive essay hinges on the writer's ability to answer a question offering strong evidence and reasoning. The ACA-401 Coursepack offers students a roadmap to this goal by breaking the essay writing process down into several smaller steps (EUCLID 2015, 1). Delving beyond the simple mechanics of essay writing, the Coursepack also provides students advice about how to start the essay writing process with research, grammar tips, commonly-confused words and other pitfalls facing novice writers.

2) RESEARCH

One of the topics highlighted in ACA-401 Coursepack is Researching the Topic. The Coursepack suggests readers do not take the first time they read through a reference material; instead, they underline or highlight the text and come back to take notes only on the second read (EUCLID 2015, 2). The notes the reader takes will become the basis of the essay but notes should not be taken during the initial read-through. I found this to be good advice because if you are concentrating on taking notes you may not be reading the material as a whole. You can lose sight of the forest for the trees so to speak. The ACA-401 Coursepack also offers good advice for the reader such as marking pages which may need to be consulted later on with post-it notes so they can be found easily later on (ibid.).

3) WRITING THE ESSAY

Part 4 of the essay writing portion of ACA-401 Coursepack focuses on Writing the Essay. Coming from a background in television news this section spoke to me the loudest, particularly the section on structure. In newswriting courses in college our mantra was always, ‘Tell them, tell them again, and then tell them what you told them.’ Essay writing tends to follow that path as well. The introduction begins with a brief outline of what you will illustrate in your paper. The body addresses the argument and the conclusion reinforces what the reader just read (EUCLID 2015, 3). The ACA-401 Coursepack suggests the writer complete a rough draft of his or her paper to see if the structure and flow actually work like he or she intended. A rough draft is the ideal time to determine whether or not the evidence and examples chosen actually satisfy your argument (ibid.).

4) EDITING

Editing can be the most difficult portion of the whole process. After days (or weeks or months) of researching and writing an academic paper, the writer must attempt to look through their own work with a fresh set of eyes. Ideally the writer will have enough time to set a few days aside away from the paper before taking on this task (EUCLID 2015, 4). When editing your work, it is important to not only look for grammatical or spelling errors but to also make sure there are no blind spots in your arguments. I always found it beneficial to have a friend who is not afraid to be critical act as my second set of fresh eyes for editing. During the editing process is also a good time to ensure you have properly followed the directions of the assignment (ibid.). You do not want to find yourself adding information to a paper you have already erroneously turned in, somehow having missed that all response papers need to be a full three pages long. Double-checking all assignment particulars during the editing process and before turning materials in can save you a great deal of embarrassment down the line.

5) PLAGIARISM

As a 15-year television news veteran the mere word plagiarism makes my blood turn a bit cold as it is seen as the ultimate sin for anyone who has ever worked as a journalist. The ACA-401 Coursepack section on plagiarism details why you always need to cite your sources and the various ways it can be done (EUCLID 2015, 5–12). In addition to the various ways quotations can be added to academic papers, the ACA-401 Coursepack also offers tips for writers to properly paraphrase works without inadvertently committing plagiarism (EUCLID 2015, 8–9). I was pleased to see so many pages be devoted to the topic of plagiarism in the Coursepack because it validates my belief that it is one of the most important topics for any writer or aspiring writer to pay attention to as they embark on any higher education or career.

6) GRAMMAR DOS AND DON'TS

Chapter 4 of the ACA-401 Coursepack includes a section on commonly confused words like your and you're, its and it's, and that versus which (EUCLID 2015, 18–19). I was pleased to see these words included in the Coursepack because I find these mistakes on an almost daily basis in emails and on social media posts. The section spelling out when to use good versus well was particularly helpful to me because this is something I often struggle with. In colloquial conversation when someone asks “How are you?” I have typically answered “Good, how are you?” because “Well, how are you?” sounds awkward to my ear even though I believe the correct answer is well. I have personally tried to get around this by retraining myself to say, “Doing well, how are you?” Another section I would find helpful would be on the proper use of there, their, and they're because much like your and you're, I see these words used incorrectly on a near-daily basis.

7) USE OF A STYLE GUIDE

ACA-401 Coursepack devotes its entire fifth chapter to why it is important to use a style guide (EUCLID 2015, 24–26). Again I will draw upon my 15 year career as a journalist and my complete devotion to the AP Stylebook. The need to follow prescribed rules of abbreviations, punctuation, and capitalizations was impressed upon me at a young age in my career and it allowed me to develop an appreciation for how much more polished a report/online news story can look when it follows the same rules and maintains the same cohesive look as its counterparts (EUCLID 2015, 24).

8) CONCLUSION

Writing a persuasive essay can be a daunting task for the inexperienced writer. Luckily, the ACA-401 Coursepack offers students some helpful tips to make this task a little easier with hints to help with essay writing, including help with research, grammar tips, how to edit your work, and how to avoid inadvertent plagiarism. The ACA-401 Coursepack is a tool any successful EUCLID student should keep in their arsenal throughout their career.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed April 7, 2020).

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.